

Fraunhofer Institute for Ceramic
Technologies and Systems IKTS

METALLICO-Demonstration of battery metals recovery from primary and secondary resources through a sustainable processing methodology

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Fraunhofer Technology Center High Performance Materials THM

Materials and processes for smart mobility, green batteries and battery recycling

- Efficient, environmentally friendly manufacturing technologies for battery electrodes
- Inline monitoring for electrodes and cell production
- Recycling of battery materials and components as well as process water treatment
- Automation of recycling processes through monitoring and database solutions
- Cooperation with TU Bergakademie Freiberg and Fraunhofer IISB

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Lithium Extraction COOL-Process

Holistic processing of primary and secondary raw materials

Recycling process validation

COOL+ Process

ZERO
WASTE

Lithium recovery from primary raw materials

Value chain

Partners involved

Challenges for cost-effective operation

COOL Process in TRL 5 possible?

Facilities at Fraunhofer IKTS - THM

200 L- Autoclave reactor

Electrodialysis

Crystallisation/
Precipitation

- Increasing **S:L ratio** for higher throughput and less wastewater production
- Connecting several reactors for quasi-continuous operation
 - Effective use of unconsumed CO₂
 - Reuse of mother liquor
 - Further utilization of process heat and pressure

Challenges for cost-effective operation

COOL Process in TRL 5 possible?

COOL-Process parameters

- Thermal pre-treatment at $T = 1100^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h
- Milling and sieving → Particle size $\leq 250 \mu\text{m}$
- Digestion with sc-CO_2 at 230°C ; 100 bar; 2h; **S:L = 1:90 – 1:45**

Challenge

- How to concentrate the Li-solution after leaching step?
 - Li-concentration in solution $\approx 10 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$ (conductivity 0.3 mS cm^{-1})
 - About 500 l of the solution

Possible solutions

- Reverse osmosis (saturation?)
- Ion exchange resin (recharging?)

Composition of the leaching residue

Results from METALLICO project produced by Fraunhofer IKTS and TUBAF

Thank you for your attention!

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